

ring protons ; and the latter shifts to δ 7.15 in the complexes indicating the involvement of thiophene ring sulphur atom in coordination.

The Ni^{II} complexes of ligand L₂ are diamagnetic and show only one band in the spectra at 16.50 kK assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ transition. In addition, bands at 8.00–10.50 and 20.00–25.00 kK may be due to ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g} + {}^3E_g$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{1g} + {}^3E_g$ transitions. These bands as well as the value of Dq (1 650 cm⁻¹) are consistent with a planar geometry⁴. The Ni^{II} complexes of ligand L₁ and L₃ on the other hand are paramagnetic (μ_{eff} around 3.00 B.M.), and in their spectra three characteristic bands at 25.00, 19.00 and 11.50 kK corresponding to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions are observed. The values of Dq , B and ν_2/ν_1 ratio around 1 150, 960 cm⁻¹ and 1.58, respectively, also confirm octahedral geometry⁵.

The μ_{eff} values ($\approx$ 5.00 B.M.) for the Co^{II} complexes are independent of temperature and correspond to three unpaired electrons and an octahedral geometry. Three bands in the electron spectra at 20.00, 16.00 and 8.00 kK are assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions, respectively. The splitting of ν_2 band as well as the values of Dq and B correspond to pseudooctahedral geometry⁶.

The μ_{eff} values of Cr^{III} complexes (around 3.73 B.M.) were very close to the spin-only value for octahedral symmetry⁷. Characteristic bands are seen at 11.80, 18.17 kK with a shoulder at 23.54 kK ; the latter band and shoulder may be assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (ν_1) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (ν_2) transition, respectively. These along with the Dq and B values which are around 1 820 and 700 cm⁻¹ correspond to octahedral coordination⁸.

The μ_{eff} values of Fe^{III} and Mn^{II} complexes are around 2.20 B.M. which correspond to their low-spin configuration having one unpaired electron. These complexes show a large number of bands in their electronic spectra around 40.00, 30.00 and 25.00 kK which are all charge transfer in nature. Ligand field transitions have been observed in the form of weak bands corresponding to Dq and B values of 3 500 and 720 cm⁻¹, respectively, and are consistent with octahedral structures⁹.

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A Corrosion Study of Welded Steel Specimens in 3% NaCl Media

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Manuscript received 27 April 1987, revised 4 December 1987,
accepted 11 December 1987

VARIOUS types of mild steel and stainless steel in welded forms are used extensively in different metallic structures. A large number of studies have been made on the corrosion of various types of metals and alloys in chloride environment¹⁻⁵. But studies of corrosion of welded steel specimens in chloride media are rather limited^{6,7}. Therefore in the present investigation corrosion studies of welded mild steel both cold rolled and hot rolled and stainless steel of the type AISI 304 have been undertaken in 3% NaCl medium to find out the nature and extend of corrosion damage.

Experimental

The steel specimens used for corrosion tests were rectangular sheets (25 × 18 × 2 mm) both in case of welded and unwelded forms. The composition of the specimens used is given in Table 1.

For welded specimens, the samples were cut into two pieces and then joined by electrical arc welding or by inert gas welding methods. Subsequently the specimens were polished on successive grades of emery paper and then washed with acetone, dried and weighed. The surface was examined under microscope. After taking the weight the specimens were subjected to electro-chemical polarisation study and for corrosion rate determination.

For the polarisation study, the specimens were taken as working electrodes. The assembly consisted of a H-type cell having a working electrode of a specific area (1 sq cm)⁸.

NOTES

TABLE 1

Specimen	Analysis %								
	O	Mn	P	S	Si	Ni	Cr	Mo	Cu
Mild (Cold rolled)	0.95	0.47	0.016	0.025	0.090	—	—	—	—
Mild steel (Hot rolled)	0.070	0.42	0.019	0.035	0.058	—	—	—	—
Stainless steel	0.047	1.58	0.045	0.03	0.48	8.08	17.7	0.28	0.018

A Wenking Potentiocan POS-73 instrument was used for potentiodynamic polarisation studies. A constant spacing of approximately 1–2 mm between the tip of the luggin capillary and working electrode surface was maintained throughout the experiments to minimise the IR drop. Platinum wire gauge of large surface area was used as a counter electrode. A solution of 3% NaCl (E. Merck) was deaerated for 12 h with nitrogen gas (99.9%). After deaeration steady state potential was achieved in 1–2 h, the specimens were kept for 96 h and steady potential was recorded with respect to the calomel electrode. Same samples were used for weight loss experiments. After the experiments, the specimens were taken out, dried and weighed. The average weight loss was recorded after similar experiments were conducted for three specimens of each type. From the weight loss, the corrosion rate was determined from the equation⁹,

$$\text{Rate (mpy)} = 534 W/DAT$$

where, W =weight loss (mg), D =density of the specimen in (g ml⁻¹), A =area of the specimen (sq inch) and T =exposure time (h).

Results and Discussion

The corrosion potential (ϕ_{corr}) evaluated from polarisation curves and the relative corrosion rate in mpy for various types of welded and unwelded mild steel and 304-stainless steel specimens, determined from the weight loss data are tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 2—RATE OF CORROSION AND CORROSION POTENTIAL OF DIFFERENT STEEL SPECIMENS

Specimens	ϕ_{corr} vs SCE, mV	Weight loss $\times 10^{-3}$ mg	Rate mpy
<i>Mild steel (cold rolled)</i>			
Gas welded	-720	1.74	10.87
Arc welded	-712	1.69	10.56
Unwelded	-700	1.81	10.06
<i>Mild steel (hot rolled)</i>			
Gas welded	-710	1.54	9.63
Arc welded	-703	1.51	9.44
Unwelded	-692	1.41	8.81
<i>Stainless steel (AISI 304)</i>			
Gas welded	-355	0.19	1.178
Arc welded	-347	0.18	1.117
Unwelded	-340	0.151	0.937

From Table 2, it can be seen that the rate of corrosion in case of cold rolled mild steel is more than the rate of corrosion of hot rolled mild steel, in chloride medium. This may be due to an increase in dislocation density and residual stresses during the cold working process, resulting in a substantial increase in strain energy in the lattice. Again strain hardening does not occur in hot worked metals since the processing temperature provides necessary thermal activation for dynamic recovery and recrystallisation in the alloy¹⁰.

As usual, the rate of corrosion of stainless steel is very much less. This is probably due to the presence of chromium, which forms a very thin stable oxide Cr_2O_3 on the surface which inhibits further corrosion attack.

Between the gas welded and arc welded specimens, the gas welded specimens corroded more quickly than that of arc welded specimens. This is due to the fact that arc welding is a better kind of welding in the sense that there was relatively better homogeneity and less impurities and less inclusions on the metal surface than that of gas welding. At the intervals of 12 h the average weight loss values were recorded.

The weight loss values were fitted to the following kinetic equation¹¹,

$$W = Kt^n$$

where, W is loss in weight (g⁻³), K and n are constant for the particular steel specimens, and t is exposure time.

Taking the logarithms, the above equation can readily be converted to the linear expression as

$$\log W = \log k + n \log t$$

The values of k and n obtained from the straight line plots of $\log W$ vs $\log t$ are presented in Table 3. From Table 3, it can be seen that the values of n and k are higher for mild steel than stainless steel. This may be due to the greater rate of corrosion attack in mild steel in comparison to the stainless steel specimens. Since n and k depend on the types of materials, the variation in their values are observed in the present case.

From Table 2, it can also be seen that the corrosion potential determined by open-circuit measurement (ϕ_{corr}) is more anodic in case of stainless steel. This may be due to the localised corrosion resistant character of stainless steels than mild steel because of the presence of chromium in

TABLE 3—LOSS IN WEIGHT AND VALUES OF n AND k OF DIFFERENT STEEL SPECIMENS

Samples	Loss in weight W in $g\ m^{-2}$	Values of n	Values of k
<i>Mild steel (cold rolled)</i>			
Gas welded	96.6	1.08	1.8
Arc welded	98.9	1.08	1.7
Unwelded	89.4	1.08	1.6
<i>Mild steel (hot rolled)</i>			
Gas welded	85.5	1.07	1.70
Arc welded	88.9	1.07	1.66
Unwelded	77.7	1.07	1.55
<i>Stainless steel (AISI-304)</i>			
Gas welded	10.5	0.8	0.22
Arc welded	10.1	0.8	0.20
Unwelded	8.3	0.8	0.18

it, and also by the fact that all the chromium present is in the solid solution and the steel has a single phase structure. In case of mild steels for hot rolled, ϕ_{corr} is more anodic than cold rolled. These results are in agreement with the finding of the rate values from weight loss methods, i.e. the corrosion rate is in the order, cold rolled mild steel > hot rolled mild steel > stainless steel. From optical microscopic studies it is revealed that the preferential corrosion attack like pit formation takes place at the welded portions of the metal surface than at the base metal.

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Effect of Particle Size on the Kinetics of Thermal Decomposition of Limestone and Marble

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Manuscript received 1 June 1987, revised 16 October 1987, accepted 7 January 1988

THE kinetic approach to the study of thermal decomposition of calcium carbonate is important because it is likely to provide basic information

about minerals, their structure etc. Whiting and Turner¹ noted the effect of grain size on the rate of decomposition of calcium carbonate. The observation of Hashimoto and Ito² reveals that the rate of thermal decomposition of calcite powder in CO₂ atmosphere is inversely proportional to the diameter of the particle. The present paper reports the effect of particle size on the kinetics of thermal decomposition of limestone and marble in air.

Experimental

The samples of limestone and marble samples were analysed following the standard procedure³.

Limestone and marble cubes (≈ 1 cm edge) with polished surfaces were prepared from cut samples. Surface area, volume and density of the cubes were determined. To study the effect of particle size on the rate of decomposition, particle sizes of between 853-422, 422-211, 211-124 and 89-64 μ were prepared from lumps of limestone and marble. Number of particles per g was calculated by the following formula presuming the particles as spheres,

$$n = \frac{6W}{\pi d^3 \rho}$$

where, n is number of particles per g of sample, W the weight of samples (g), d the average diameter of each particle (cm) and ρ the density of sample ($g\ cm^{-3}$). The surface area (S) was calculated by the following formula, $S = n\pi d^2$.

The weight loss of the samples was recorded in a thermobalance at suitable time intervals and in an atmosphere of CO₂ to prevent early decomposition of the sample.

Results and Discussion

Density and composition of the samples are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DENSITY AND COMPOSITION OF SAMPLES

Source	Limestone Jhinkpani (L ₁ , wt%)	Limestone Cuddapah (L ₂ , wt%)	Marble Makrana (M, wt%)
Loss on ignition	98.01	96.05	43.51
SiO ₂	10.65	23.90	0.81
Al ₂ O ₃	2.66	0.13	0.21
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.55	0.11	0.03
CaO	47.06	21.70	54.98
MgO	0.64	15.95	0.27
Density ($g\ cm^{-3}$)	2.717	2.704	2.719

It was felt that some modification of the equation, $(W/W_0)^{1/3} = 1 - k't$, derived by Britton *et al.*⁴ was necessary to explain the discrepancy observed by them. It was presumed that the decomposition of calcium carbonate occurs at the interface advancing from the surface of the particle to the interior. It was also considered that since it is a reversible